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Virtue Ethics For Human And National Development

Prof. Ngangah; Rev. Fr. Prof. Eugene Anowai & Innocent Anthony Uke

**Department of Philosophy,
Faculty of Arts,
Chukwu Emeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam, Anambra State, Nigeria**

ABSTRACT

In a world saturated with all manner of socio-cultural, religious, economic and political vices such as nepotism, bribery and corruption etc., there comes a belief or an assumption that it makes little or no sense continuing to sound the relevance of living a virtuous life. No doubt, our contemporary world and culture is vigorously besieged with various forms of debilitating theories, perspectives and ideologies that tend to make any call for virtuous life seemingly unreasonable, such theories and worldviews as liberalism, relativism, and emotivism among others, grossly appear to be the leading forces that direct and redirect human affairs in our contemporary world. The question, however, that seeks for answer, in the midst of all these, remains: Is virtue ethics still relevant for human and national development? The present paper attempts to answer in the affirmative as it lays down the principles of virtue ethics in seeing to the development of the human person and his society. The work, which is though largely expository in presentation and analytic in argument, offers to show or demonstrate the continuing significance of living a virtuous life in the face of many vicissitudes of life as evident in the world that we all live today.

Keywords: Ethics, national development, virtue

INTRODUCTION

Simply put, virtue ethics is a framework that focuses on the character of the moral agent rather than the rightness of an action. It is a way of thinking about how to behave well which has not received a great deal of attention within the discipline of international relation. Virtue ethic is a theory that sees virtues and vices as central to understanding who we should be and what we should do. As a philosophy developed by Aristotle and other ancient Greeks, it is the quest to understand and live a life of moral character. It relates to the ethical theory that emphasizes the cultivation of certain positive character traits as the aim of moral activity. It also emphasizes the role of character and virtue in moral philosophy rather than either doing one's duty or acting (Udoiem, 1992).

In a world that is confronted by all manner of socio-cultural, religious, economic and political vices such as nepotism, bribery and corruption etc., some people have argued that it makes little or no sense continuing to sound the relevance of living a virtuous life. They believe that our world today, no doubt, shows that majority of us—human beings—live a life obsessed with all manner self-love that involves one's feelings or actions for oneself alone without any intervening concerns about how others are affected. People seem to have total lack of motivation for authentic moral judgment. As such, virtue is on the wane and morality has been misrepresented variously as either liberalism, or relativism or situation ethics or emotivism (Amaku,2010). Consequently, mortal values have lost its objectivity; hence the customization of science of ethics wherein one's responsibilities to others are mutilated by the isolated

self with claims of rights, self-interest and freedom. Significantly, we neglect the moral character of the human animality, vulnerability, disability, weakness, mistakes, and dependence. Consequently also, the human authentic life appears to presuppose freedom without control. It is based on this that this paper x-rays the continuing relevance of virtue ethics for human survival and flourishing even in our contemporary time.

Greek Foundation of Virtue Ethics at a Glance

Traditionally, the pre-Socratics were said to be pre-ethical philosophers. This means that theirs was the tradition that made Socrates responsible for the ethical turn that he canvassed and that we all have till today. A look at the early Greek philosophers, for example, shows somewhat an abundance of views and arguments that could be rightly termed ethical. For example, Xenophanes' critique of the Homeric gods and the construction of a rational philosopher's gods, including the Pythagorean and Empedoclean theories with the Orphics, all reveal how good and bad behavior are connected with the fate of the soul after death (Plato, *Apology* 28bc). And this can be referred to as ethics. Although the ancient therefore showed much dependence on several notions about virtue, it was clear that the idea of virtue, perhaps understood as happiness (*eudemonia*) in the case of Aristotle and the soul, was very central to them (Plato, *Crito* 47e-48a).

In the *Apology*, Socrates championed the view that a man that is worth anything at all does not reckon with whether his cause of action endangers his life or threatens death. Instead, he thinks it is the consideration of whether his action is just or unjust that matters. Consequently, Socrates argues in the *Crito* that virtue is a psychological good of first importance. Plato's Socrates in the *Meno* discusses the intellectualism of morality arguing that no body desires evil unknowingly. Virtue, he claims, is knowledge and vice ignorance (Plato, *Apology* 28bc). In the *Republic* IX, Plato's Socrates describes *eudemonia* as the most important and the dominant constituent of happiness. Virtue, he says, is the *Imitation of Form* and a state of the soul expressible in the welfare of oneself and that of the city (Plato, *Republic* Bk IX, 580d-e, 583=587a-e).

In his *Nicomachean Ethics*, Aristotle defines moral virtue as a disposition to behave in the right manner and as a mean between extremes of deficiency and excess which are vices. Aristotle taught that people develop virtuous life because it brings about happiness, which is the highest good defined as an activity of the rational soul in accordance with virtue. Aristotle recognizes two kinds of virtue, namely moral virtue, which includes *Arete* (courage, temperance, pride, gentleness, wittiness, etc.) and intellectual virtue which includes theoretical wisdom, science) (*episteme*), intuitive understanding (*nous*), practical wisdom (*phronesis*), prudence and craft expertise. There are therefore three fundamental concepts in Aristotle's thought that define virtue ethics, namely excellent character (*Arete*), practical wisdom (*phronesis*) and well-being—flourishing or sustainable happiness (*eudemonia*) (Aristotle, bk ii, chapter 6, 7, 1106b-1107a).

Diogenes Laertius has his view that freedom from unnecessary desires is embedded in simple natural life not in convention. He also maintains that such natural life is essential to virtue although Aristippus denies that virtue is necessary for achieving happiness (Laertius, *Delphi Complete Works of Diogenes Laertius*, vi, 69-70). Epicurus appears to have associated virtue with pleasure when he thinks that all human actions should be geared toward pleasure. However, he thinks pleasure must be qualified because some pleasures can lead to pain/evil (Epicurus, *Letter to Menoecus*, 128-129)

Virtue Ethics in the Patristic and Modern Periods

The patristic era witnessed a controversial moment in the debate about virtue ethics. It was a period the church fathers allowed their Christian background to influence their choices of words, thoughts and action about virtue ethics (Stoics, *Stoicorum Veterum Fragmenta*, vol. iv). It was the era that saw St. Augustine defining virtue as 'the perfect love of God'. Augustine saw virtue as 'good use of choice' (St. Augustine, *Loannem*, 15.12). Some commentators of Anselm's notion of virtue argue that for Anselm, it is 'the good mores and qualities of the soul which brings about the condition of habit that is achievable through living

a virtuous life.’ On that basis, Anselm contends that charity must be loved and pursued more than knowledge because all useful knowledge, law and the prophets depend on charity (Saint Anselm, *Eadmer Vita Sancti Anselmi*). Peter Abellard proclaimed that virtue entails happiness (Abelard, 2018).

Aquinas’ belief that virtue is a good faculty or power of good bearing on activity indicates his Platonic/Aristotelian foundation which saw virtue as a presupposition of the possession of masculine qualities such as strength, and courage which promote moral order of goodness and human perfection. Consequently, Aquinas believes that virtue is the order of love (Aquinas, 1948).

In the metaphysics of virtue, Don Scotus contends that a human being is good to the extent that he has virtues. This implies that morality is not just tied to human flourishing rather it is impossible to be moral without being libertarily free (Hardron, 2021).

It was up to Hume to speak of virtue ethics as moral only when it creates peace, promotes happiness through rooted in law. Beyond that, he argues that virtue is whatever mental action or quality gives to a spectator the pleasing sentiment of approbation; that is a feeling of satisfaction of particular kind from the contemplation of a character (Hume, 2012).

Kant’s Groundwork of Metaphysics shows his conviction that ancient virtues such as moderation, self-control and calm reflection are conducive to the goodwill but that that the goodness of the good will does not depend on them (Kant, 1964).

From the above, one can see the dialogical sequence following the potentiality of virtue ethic in building a sound and authentic human flourishing and engendering proper national development.

The Concept of National Development and Human Flourishing

An idea of national development presupposes an understanding of what a nation is. According to Mathew Nwoko (2006), the term ‘nation’ means a people sharing a common language (or dialect of a common language), inhabiting a fixed territory, with common customs and tradition, which may have become sufficiently conscious to take on the aspect of law, and who recognizes common interest and a common need for a single sovereign. For him, a people as a nation must be united under a common ethnic heritage, origin or ancestry. Nwoko further accentuates that members of the nation must feel themselves naturally linked together by certain affinities which are so strong and real for them that they can live happily together, and are dissatisfied when disunited and cannot tolerate subjection from people who do not share these ties. Also, in the view of Nwoko, we could then outline the following as the major characteristics of a nation: a community of people, common natural sentiments of loyalty and identity, common ethnic heritage, common territory and future, history and sovereignty not limited to specific purposes (Nwoko, 2006:32).

On the other hand, the concept of development cannot be easily defined. However, as noted by Walter Rodney (1992), it is “a many-sided process.” Because of this many-sided nature, I would prefer not to border the reader with excessive tedious terminological and definitional discussions rather, I would like to offer a new interpretation that would be universally applicable to the many-sidedness or various dimensions of development. The interpretation will be person-centered.

According to Rodney (1992: 96), at the level of the individual person, development implies “increased skill and capacity, greater freedom, creativity, self-discipline, responsibility, and material well-being.” But for Rodney, the achievement of any of these aspects of personal development is very much tied in with the state of the society as a whole. It might be pointed out here that it is in this last remark that Rodney’s mistake about development is constituted. He seems to have subsumed the person within the social structure as a necessary condition for development. The position of this paper is that the reverse seems to be the case. For both socio-economic and political conditions are contingent on the individual person’s development (Rodney, 1992).

Sir Francis Ellah, in his book, *Nigerian society and Governance*, subscribes to this idea of development originating from person and being person centered. He noted this when he wrote:

No development can occur in the absence of Freedom, because without freedom we are in bondage, and bondage is slavery, which is the lowest degradation to which human nature can fall, which is the very opposite of development. There can be no development if men are ignorant, intimidated, poor and sick in body and mind... There is no development if man himself, is not developed in his body and in mind (Ellah, 1987: 107).

The crucial point in Ella's submission is the issue of freedom as *a conditio sine qua non* and since freedom resides primarily in the person, it could be concluded that development must begin with the person. Ella's next claim is that there can be no development if men are ignorant and sick in body and mind. Here again, the emphasis is on the person as the focus of development.

A synthesis of both Walter Rodney and Francis Ellah's submission reveals that development can be defined as a process leading to the realization of full human and environmental potentials. If therefore, in our thrust towards human/community/national development, the full human and environmental potentials are not realized, then the human person/ nation or community is yet to be developed.

Having said that, we now come to the idea of human flourishing. This idea of human flourishing indicates the idea of freedom of the individual. However, Njoku (2001) thinks that human flourishing implies acting morally. Following the thinking of Plato, he contends that acting morally means acting

in a such a way that, as are adapted to one's individual capacities, one contributes by doing one's tasks without mingling in those of others. The reason for doing this is the place where the highest excellences should be cultivated, individuals realize their full potentials by acting morally (Njoku, 2001: 87).

However, it is obvious the why of morality in Plato's system will be to bring harmony or equilibrium both in the individual and in the state. However, Aristotle, Plato's disciple, believes that the participation in harmony of the state as *eudemonia*, that is, happiness.

John Finnis and the Basic Goods of Human Flourishing

For Finnis (1980), life is the first basic good which puts a human being in good shape for self-determination. It encompasses bodily health, freedom from pain and so on. Without intending to say that procreation, sexual expression of love and friendship are analytically the same, Finnis is convinced that the aforementioned values are reducible to one basic value—life. Finnis identified basic goods of human flourishing as 'knowledge, play, aesthetic experience, sociability (friendship), practical reasonableness, and religion' (Finnis, 1980: 87).

Talking about knowledge, he sees knowledge as an aspect of human flourishing, is an intrinsic good. It is considered to be desirable for its own sake and not merely as something sought after under some such description as 'what will enable me to impress my audience' or 'what will confirm my instinctive beliefs' or 'what will contribute to my survival.' In sum... to say that such knowledge is a value is simply to say that reference to the pursuit of knowledge makes -intelligible (though not necessarily reasonable -all-things-considered) any particular instance of the human activity and commitment involved in such pursuit (Finnis, 1980:62).

Although the good of knowledge is self-evident, the principle that knowledge is worth pursuing is not innate, for value is not deducible from facts; that some educated elite in Africa have failed their people is not a reason to be dissuaded from pursuing knowledge. On the other hand, that all men seek knowledge is again not a reason to pursue it for the universality of a desire is not a basis for arguing that it is objectively good.

But to say that knowledge must be a real value, because intelligent men, or great men, or mature men have regarded it as a value and as an aspect of their own flourishing, is not to make what could be called an inference. For one's assessment of a person as flourishing, mature, good, or, in the relevant respect, intelligent is made possible only by one's own underived understanding that what that person is and does is really good (in the relevant respects). The 'premises of the apparent inference rests on its condition (Finnis, 1980:67).

On its own right then, knowledge is simply good and worthy of pursuing.

With regard to play, Finnis appreciates the insight of anthropologists who see play as an irreducible element in human culture. People engage in performance, which evidences their place and solidarity in the world. Thus, Finnis writes:

The performance may be solitary or social, intellectual or physical, strenuous or relaxed, highly structured or relatively informal, conventional or ad hoc in its pattern...An element of play can enter into any human activity, even in drafting of enactments, but is always analytically distinguishable from its 'serious' context (Finnis, 1980:87).

The spirit of human experience is lubricated through play or through the spirit of mutual embodiment in the world. Performance is a gateway to the being of humans in the community of sharing of meaning and social solidarity.

According to Finnis, the fourth basic good of human flourishing is aesthetic experience. This is seen when forms of play such as dance, folktales and songs become occasions for aesthetic experience. Finnis thinks that aesthetic experience needs not to involve an action of one's own as in play. This is because 'what is sought after and valued for its own sake may simply be the beautiful form 'outside' one and the 'inner' experience of appreciation of its beauty (Finnis, 1980:88). Thus, aesthetic experience primarily involves the appreciation that the works of human expressions are forms in their own right. Pure experience of aesthetes is a justification of its own existence, an instance of satisfaction of the human spirit.

Sociability or friendship is the fifth among the basic goods of human flourishing. According to Finnis, humans are certainly born for society, for 'some of the collaboration between one person and another is no more than instrumental to the realization by each of his own individual purposes (Finnis, 1980:88). There are some who think that humans are fundamentally selfish, but as it is the case, there are others who hold contrary view. These opposite views indicate that people can act, not solely for their own personal interests. As Finnis indicates, friendship involves acting for the sake of one's friend's well-being (Finnis, 1980: 88). We are not being fundamentally selfish when we act for friendship's sake or enhance people who are associated with us. It is a form of good to be in friendship.

Being the sixth basic good, practical reasonableness, according to Finnis, borders on being able to bring one's own intelligence to bear effectively on the problems of choosing one's actions and life-style and shaping one's own character (Finnis, 1980:88). On the negative sense, practical reasonableness puts an effective check on one's freedom; however, positively, it counsels that one brings intelligence and reasonable order to critique one's actions, habits, and practical attitudes. On the whole, practical reasonableness involves an internal aspect or organization and ordering of one's emotions in a harmonious fashion.

Religion is the seventh of all these basic goods according to Finnis. According to him, after the recognition of order as means to ends, pursuit of life, truth, play, aesthetic experience which one lived and substantiated in human relations and community, then arises the question of the relationship of these human orders to a lasting order which grounds all (human) orders and values. The answer to this question cannot be overlooked as Finnis believes that human concerns go beyond the basic goods of the limited order (Finnis, 1980). Therefore, one's sense of responsibility is not restricted to the concern to live, play, procreate and so on. There is, in humans, recognition of a source that grounds all human aspirations or gives meaning to the longings of humans for ultimate happiness or peace.

On the final note, Finnis notes that these basic goods motivate us as reasons for action. They are objective goods and are attainable in a community of human beings where there is a legal system.

Methodological Requirements of Practical Reasonableness as Conditions for Human and National Development

In a work titled: *The Reason Why a Human Being Should act Morally*, FOC Njoku (2003), underlines how basic facts about the human beings, are. For him, the fact is that humans are created by God, and that they have a characteristic that separates them from other animals. That characteristic, he admits, is reason. Against this background, he lists some major explanations derivable from the points made above about why humans should act morally.

First and foremost, deriving a point from a biblico/theological point of view, he sees morality as conducting oneself in the world in one's relationship with others and with God. For Njoku, since we are created by God, and He wants us to imitate him in his life, goodness and perfection, therefore the reason to be moral is simply that God commands it; because He wants us to indulge in conducts that will help us share in his life. To be moral is to act in a way that is God-like in the measure in which it is possible for humans (Njoku, 2003).

We have noted earlier that Plato believes that morality pays for the individual, as he expresses through the mouth of Socrates. For Socrates, to be moral is to seek the way of virtue or truth that will lead to the truth about reality, and lead humans to act accordingly. This is demonstrated in Plato's Dialogue called *Euthyphro*. Between Socrates and Euthyphro, one comes to grip with the strength and weakness of the religious basis of morality. In Apology, Socrates insists on the truth of his position, while exposing the false claims of his accusers. Socrates wants to know what virtue is and participate in it.

Whether or not it is the basic good of practical reasonableness or the reason why a human being should be moral, that leads to human and national development, Finnis has pointed out some methodological requirements for the realization of complete human and national development.

According to him, a person or society can achieve proper development if there is a consistent plan of life. For Finnis, the basic aspects of human well-being "are discernable only to one who thinks about opportunities, and thus are realizable only by one who intelligently directs, focuses, and controls his urges, inclination, and impulses. In other words, they are achievable by one with an effective plan of life. No plan is achieved by living on the spur of the moment (Finnis, 1988:102).

Another basic methodological requirement, according to Finnis, is no arbitrary preferences amongst values. What this means is that commitment to a coherent plan of life will involve some degree of concentration. While people make their choices of value, they should pay attention to others and their plans of life. In other words, one's plan of life must make reasonable allowance for the horizon of participation in intrinsic human values by others (Finnis, 1988: 100-125).

No arbitrary preferences amongst values involves too no arbitrary preferences amongst persons. It shows that human beings must always be taken into consideration in our choices. Human beings participate in the goods and realize them. Although a person's survival, being, progress and creativity may not interest me, I have no reason to deny that they are real goods. We are all responsible for the well-being of all; the basic goods concern everyone.

Beyond no arbitrary preferences amongst persons is detachment according to Finnis in the sequence of the basic methodological requirements. Detachment shows that

humans need to be open to all the basic forms of good in their changing and challenging circumstances of a lifetime in the midst of openness to life's opportunities of counsels for the need to be detached so that, in those circumstances when sincere and good efforts in the pursuit of human goods are not matched with corresponding and glaring success, one would not consider life as 'drained of meaning'

Detachment demonstrates that doing something worthwhile and sensible remains a good thing independent of results of success/progress or failure. An attitude of desperation in the midst of authentic human pursuits

irrationally devalues and treats as meaningless the basic human goods of authentic and reasonable self-determination, a good in which one meaningfully participates simply by trying to do something sensible and worthwhile, whether or not that sensible and worthwhile project comes to nothing.

It is along this line that Finnis argues that detachment is included as a requirement of practical reasonableness.

To go along with detachment is commitment, according to Finnis. Commitment establishes the balance between fanaticism and dropping out, apathy, unreasonableness, failure or refusal 'to get involved' with anything. Commitment entails one to find new and creative ways of going beyond mere stipulations of convention and conformity in instantiating the practical principles of reasonableness.

Furthermore, Finnis recognizes that commitment is followed by the requirement of common good. This is a common good in terms of concrete moral responsibilities, obligations and duties that go to foster the well-being of communities. Finnis distinguishes three senses of the common good, namely common good in the sense that they are good to life, knowledge, play, aesthetic expression, friendship, religion and freedom in practical reasonableness are good for any and every person. Second is that they are common good as far as individuals can participate in an inexhaustible way in each of the basic human values in their various circumstances.

The third sense understands common good as 'a set of conditions which enables the members of a community to attain for themselves reasonable objectives, or to realize reasonably for themselves the value(s), for the sake of which they have reason to collaborate with each other (positively) and or negatively) in a community.

This is followed by another common good which Finnis regards as following one's conscience. This is a requirement that one should not do what one judges or thinks or feels-all-in-all should not be done. In all the basic goods and the methodological requirements together provide the criterion for distinguishing ways of acting that are morally right or wrong.

Finnis's position reveals the basic requirements for human and national development. It bears on the value of virtuous life.

Relationship Between Moral Values (Basic Requirements) and Human and National Development

We have shown in this work how virtue ethics is necessary for both human and national development. What is left at this point is to demonstrate how in practical terms these moral values can be domesticated in daily practices to ensure human and national development. First and foremost, we must have in mind that moral values are principles, goals, standards and ways of life held or accepted as desirable by an individual, class or society. The question is, do these values negate or enhance the realization of full human potential whether of an individual or of a group of individual and or of community? Values are said to be moral worth if they are cherished ways of life that promote mutual welfare, ensure the common good of man as man and as enhance the realization of the full human and national potentials. If therefore, the individual or class values do not foster the good of other human beings, the society at large or the nations, then such values have no moral worth.

At this point, we shall demonstrate the relationship between these basic requirements which we refer here now as moral values in promoting and enhancing human and national development. One fact is clear; it is that every human and society year for survival or development. Therefore, these basic requirements are sine qua non for this to come into play or full realization.

CONCLUSION

Human and national development is something possible to have if humans make up their minds to achieve them. As it is said, human beings search for happiness in an endless variety of ways—through pleasure, political power, wealth, literary fame—but a few of them think of attaining this happiness by living the virtuous life. No doubt Aristotle teaches us in his ethical and political treatises that we cannot ignore morality in our search for happiness, for “we cannot have happiness unless we have complete goodness in a complete lifetime” (Aristotle, 1968: Bk. 1. Ch.9). On this note, this paper has demonstrated the role and relevance of virtue ethics in the development of the human person and his society. Like Mbukanma (2000), right noted, every nation or society aspiring to develop should not overlook the impact that virtuous life makes. Countries of the world where real development has taken place are those who have cherished virtuous life over every other thing. Before the colonization of Africa, it was customary that the traditional African sees the good life not so much in the possession of these things but in the way a person conducts his moral life. For them, a good name (*‘Ezi afa’* in Igbo) is far more desirable and commendable than the good things of this life. A good person is that person, who in each act he/she does or refrain from doing, seeks the good of all persons who are affected by his/her actions. The morally good person thinks not only of himself/herself but of the good of the community as well. In a bid for his/her own personal good however, he/she makes sure that he/she does no harm to other people’s interest. On that note therefore, this paper concludes that virtue ethics remains relevant to our contemporary time even as it appears that the challenges of life continue to affect how we live and ought to live.

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